

Anthraquinone and dihydroflavonol from *Cassia angustifolia*

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Manuscript received 7 July 1999, revised 22 May 2001, accepted 17 August 2001

5,7,4'-Trihydroxy-6,8,3',6'-tetramethoxy-2,3-dihydroflavonol and 1-hydroxy-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylanthraquinone have been isolated from the seeds of *Cassia angustifolia*.

Cassia angustifolia Vahl.¹ (Leguminosae) is valuable in medicine for its cathartic properties and the pods of this plant have powerful laxative effects². Polysaccharides³, emodin, sennosides, anthraquinone derivatives⁵, senescence⁶, anthraquinone and bianthrone⁷, galactomannan and xyloglucan⁸ have been reported earlier from this plant. Herein we report the isolation and characterization of anthraquinone and dihydroflavonol from the seeds of *C. angustifolia*. The plant was collected from Dehradun, India (identified with the help of Botany Department, Allahabad University, Allahabad).

The air-dried and defatted seeds (4 kg) of *C. angustifolia* were extracted with boiling EtOH. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure, then chromatographed over a silica gel flash column using different organic solvents in increasing order of polarity. Individual fractions were worked out separately. Benzene-ethyl acetate (8 : 2, v/v) fraction was found to contain compound-A and pure ethyl acetate fraction gave compound-B, homogenous on TLC.

Compound-A showed a molecular ion peak in the mass spectrum at m/z 408 in agreement with the formula $C_{19}H_{20}O_{10}$. Its IR spectrum (KBr) exhibited strong absorptions at 3420 (OH) and 1630 cm^{-1} (chelated C=O). It gave violet colour with alcoholic $FeCl_3$, a dark blue colour with Gibbs reagent, and a pink colour with $Mg-HCl$ ⁹. Its UV spectrum in MeOH (ν_{max} 292, 320 nm) suggested a flavanone¹⁰ or dihydroflavonol structure. A bathochromic shift of band I (27 nm) in its UV spectrum in the presence of $AlCl_3$ indicated the presence of a free hydroxyl group at C-5¹¹. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the compound-A in DMSO- d_6 showed an AB type system due to C-2 and C-3 methine protons of dihydroflavonol¹² at δ 5.25 and 4.52 respectively. The J value of these two methine protons is typical of diaxial coupling¹². Three broad signals at δ 12.10, 11.80 and 9.25 were assigned to one chelated hydroxyl group at C-5 and non-chelated hydroxyl groups at C-7 and C-4'. Compound-A formed a tetra-acetate indicating the presence of four hydroxyl groups in the molecule. The signals due to H-2' ap-

peared at δ 6.98 and H-5' proton signal at δ 7.05^{3,10}. Four three-proton singlets at δ 3.95, 3.98, 4.03 and 4.10 indicated the presence of four methoxyl groups. Compound-A gave the positive colour reaction with vanillin hydrochloric acid reagent¹⁴, which showed the presence of 1/3-dihydroxy system in the compound. The bathochromic shift of 9 nm in band I with NaOAc revealed the presence of hydroxyl group at C-7¹⁰ and the bathochromic shift of 24 nm with H_3BO_3 -NaOAc in band I supported the phenolic hydroxyl group at C-4' of ring B¹⁵. Compound-A was soluble in aqueous sodium carbonate confirming the presence of hydroxyl groups at C-7 and C-4'¹⁶ and the presence of 4'-hydroxyl group was also confirmed by bathochromic shifts of 50 and 45 nm in band I with NaOMe and NaOAc, respectively¹⁰. Thus the structure of compound-A was established as 5,7,4'-trihydroxy-6,8,3',6'-tetramethoxy-2,3-dihydroflavonol. It was further supported by its mass spectrum, which showed a molecular ion peak at m/z 408, an $[A_1]^+$ fragment at m/z 212 consistent with an A-ring with two hydroxyl and two methoxyl groups and a $[B_1]^+$ fragment at m/z 196 consistent with the presence of one hydroxyl and two methoxyl groups in the B-ring. This new compound is reported for the first time from natural source.

Compound-B showed UV bands characteristic of anthraquinone derivative^{17,18} and IR bands suggested it to be a tetra-substituted anthraquinone¹⁹. On zinc dust distillation compound-B gave 2-methylanthracene²⁰. The ¹H NMR spectrum exhibited a signal at δ 2.45 for the presence of a methyl group at β -position²¹. It also showed the signals for two methoxyl groups in compound-B. Compound-B did not give the positive test for 1,8-dihydroxy system but its demethylated product gave this test²². It was therefore evident that the hydroxyl group is located at C-1 and one methoxyl group at C-8. Compound-B showed ¹H NMR peaks at δ 6.87, 7.12, 7.37 and 7.63 for aromatic protons and the coupling constants of these doublets indicated that all these protons were *meta*-coupled. On acetylation with acetic anhydride/pyridine at room temperature, compound-

B gave monoacetate signal at δ 2.12. The presence of hydroxyl group in compound-B was confirmed by positive colour reaction (Somogyi)²³. The structural assignment was further supported by the ¹³C NMR spectrum. This structure was also supported by mass fragmentation peak at M⁺ 298 and showed the intense peaks at *m/z* 270 and 242 respectively due to successive elimination of carbon monoxide, characteristic of anthraquinone²⁴. Thus, compound-B was characterized as 1-hydroxy-6,8-dimethoxy-3-methylanthraquinone. This compound is reported for the first time from natural source.

Experimental

The air-dried crushed seeds (4 kg) of *C. angustifolia* were extracted with boiling petroleum ether. Defatted seeds were then extracted with boiling ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated and then chromatographed over a silica gel flash column using different organic solvents in increasing order of polarity. Compound-A (110 mg) was obtained from C₆H₁₂-C₂H₅OAc (8 : 2, v/v) fraction and compound-B (176 mg) isolated from pure ethyl acetate as eluant.

Compound-A : M.p. 187° (Found : C, 55.88; H, 4.91. C₁₉H₂₀O₁₀ calcd. for : C, 55.90; H, 4.95%), *R_f* = 0.58; ν_{\max} (MeOH) 292, 320 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3420 (OH), 1630 cm⁻¹ (C=O); ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆; 100 MHz) 3.95 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.98 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.03 (3H, s, OCH₃) 4.10 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.52 (1H, d, *J* 11 Hz), 5.25 (1H, d, *J* 11 Hz), 6.98 (1H, s, H-2'), 7.05 (1H, s, H-5'), 12.10 (1H, s, C-5), 11.80 (1H, s, C-7), 9.25 (1H, s, C-4') EIMS (70 eV) *m/z* 408 (M)⁺ 212, 196.

Compound-B : M.p. 215° (benzene : ethyl acetate, 5 : 5 v/v) (Found : C, 68.47; H, 4.71. C₁₇H₁₄O₅ calcd. for : C, 68.45; H, 4.69), *R_f* = 0.61; ν_{\max} (MeOH) 258, 261, 288, 415 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3336, 2918, 1672, 1625, 1452, 1186 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃; 100 MHz) 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.62 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.98 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.12 (3H, s, CH₃COO, monoacetate), 6.87 (1H, d, *J* 2.3 Hz, H-7), 7.12 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-2), 7.37 (1H, d, *J* 2.3 Hz, H-4), 7.63 (1H, d, *J* 2.3 Hz, H-5), 12.55 (1H, s, H-1); ¹³C NMR δ (CDCl₃; 100 MHz) 160.1 (s, C-1), 123.40 (d, C-2), 149.0 (s, C-3), 109.10 (d, C-4), 108.70 (d, C-5), 163.80 (s, C-6), 107.20 (d, C-7), 164.85 (s, C-8), 184.12 (s, C-9), 182.00

(s, C-10), 135.1 (s, C-11), 112.5 (s, C-12), 114.0 (s, C-13), 140.0 (s, C-14), 24.25 (q, CH₃), 55.8 (q, OCH₃), 56.90 (q, OCH₃); EIMS (70 eV) *m/z* 298 (M)⁺ 270.

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